

Simple and Rapid Detection of Cations and Anions on modified Anion Exchange Resin

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Spot test is an elegant rapid and sensitive technique of analysis¹. The resin spot test developed by Fujimoto² has several advantages. The resin beads adsorb metal ion and give the characteristic colour of the complex³. The resin beads have also been used for the detection of organic compounds⁴. It is possible to detect even traces because of small surface area of the beads. The resins sorbed with different chelating agents may show marked selectivity towards a particular metal ion. Hence, efforts have been made to develop new chelate form of exchange resins and to find their specificity for the detection of metal ions as well as anions. Aromatic chelating agents⁵ have been considerably used for the separation of metal ions on anion exchange resins⁶. In the present communication, we report the usefulness of bromophenol blue (BPB) and bromothymol blue (BTB) sorbed anion exchange resin for the detection of cations and anions at μg level.

Results and Discussion

Among the various materials tried, e.g. silica gel, Dowex 50W $\times$ 8 and Amberlite IR-120, only alumina and Amberlite IRA-400 gave satisfactory results since both BPB and BTB could be irreversibly adsorbed on these sorbents. After sorption of BTB or BPB the colour of the resin beads changed from yellow to dark green and dark blue respectively. Amberlite resin loaded with different chelating agents shows potentiality for the detection of both cations and anions. However, BPB appears to be the most promising for the detection of cations and anions. Detection of cations was also performed in solution phase for comparison. The resin bead test appears to be more sensitive. Thus Fe^{III} ($0.8 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was identified in a mixture containing (amount $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in parenthesis) Ni^{II} (0.8), Co^{II} (0.8), Mn^{II} (0.8), Ca^{II} (0.6), Pb^{II} (3.0) and Cr^{III}

(0.8) on alumina modified with BPB. The metal ions studied showed colour change except Pb^{II} ($20.8 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) on alumina loaded with BTB. Therefore, this test can be used for testing the purity of the lead sample. The contamination of other metal ions even in traces in a synthetic mixture gave a colour change.

In order to show the practical utility of this method, synthetic mixtures of a number of metal ions were prepared and detected for the specific metal ion. It was found that contamination (amount $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in parenthesis) of Fe^{III} (0.8) and Cr^{III} (0.8) even in traces in the mixture containing Ni^{II} (0.8), Co^{II} (0.8), Mn^{II} (0.8), Ca^{II} (0.6) and Pb^{II} (3.0) gave distinct colour with BPB form of the Amberlite IRA-400. Identification of Hg^{II} ($20 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and Fe^{II} ($5.6 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) from other bivalent metal ions was done on Amberlite IRA-400 modified with BPB. Similarly, identification (amount $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in parenthesis) of Ho^{III} (2.8) in a mixture of rare earths Pr^{III} (2.4), Gd^{III} (2.6), Y^{III} (1.4), Er^{III} (2.8) and Yb^{III} (2.8) was done using this material. Al^{III} ($0.8 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) did not give any colour change. Thus it was possible to distinguish Al^{III} ($0.8 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) in the presence of Cr^{III} ($1.8 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and Fe^{III} ($1.8 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$).

Experiments revealed that most of the metal ions could be identified conveniently even if these are present in less than ppm level in a sample. The detection limit (amount $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in parenthesis) for various metal ions is standardised as follows: Pr^{III} (17.4), Gd^{III} (19.4), Y^{III} (11.0), Er^{III} (20.8), Yb^{III} (21.4), Ho^{III} (20.4), Cr^{III} (6.4), Al^{III} (3.4), Fe^{III} (7.0), Sr^{II} (10.8), Ca^{II} (5.0), Ba^{II} (17.0), Zn^{II} (8.2), Mg^{II} (3.0), Cd^{II} (14.0), Pb^{II} (25.6), Mn^{II} (6.8), Ni^{II} (7.2), Co^{II} (7.4), Cu^{II} (7.8), Hg^{II} (24.8) and Ag^{I} (13.4).

Similarly, it was possible to distinguish between

$\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ using BPB loaded resin. Selective identification of MnO_4^- , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$, CrO_4^{2-} and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ was done in the presence of a large number of other anions of diverse nature, viz. SO_4^{2-} , SO_3^{2-} , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , ClO_3^- , SCN^- , MoO_4^{2-} , I^- , Br^- , F^- and SeO_3^{2-} . It is interesting to note that $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and CrO_4^{2-} behave differently in aqueous hydrochloric acid, and therefore they can be differentiated. To check its practical applicability in the presence of other anions, a particular anion was detected successfully, in a synthetic mixtures of other anions. The results are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1 – SELECTIVE DETECTION OF CHROMATE, DICHROMATE AND PERMANGANATE IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURE OF ANIONS ON RESIN BEADS BPB FORM

Original colour of resin beads : yellow; Colour of modified resin beads : dark blue

Sl. no.	Mixtures medium	Neutral medium	Alkaline medium	Acidic medium	Result
1.	Sulphate-nitrate-chlorate-chromate-iodate	Dark green	Dark green	Light green	Chromate present
2.	Sulphite-nitrite-thiosulphate-perchlorate-dichromate	Dark green	Dark green	Light green	Dichromate present
3.	Chloride-bromide-iodide-fluoride-permanganate	Black	Black	Black	Permanganate present

Experimental

Glacial acetic acid, sodium acetate, ammonia solution, sodium hydroxide, hydrochloric acid (all B.D.H.) were used. EDTA (S. D. Fine Chem.), bromophenol blue (BPB), bromothymol blue (BTB) and other chemicals were of analytical grade. Amberlite

IRA-400 (Cl^- -form) resin (B.D.H.) was used.

Preparation of modified form of resin : The resin (~ 40 g) in Cl^- -form (20–50 mesh) was equilibrated for 24 h with 1 g dm^{-3} solution (200 ml) of either BPB or BTB to convert it into the desired form with intermittent shaking at room temperature. The supernatant liquid was removed and the resin was rinsed several times with demineralised water by the process of decantation and then finally washed in a column until the excess reagent was completely removed. The resin beads were dried in an oven at $60 \pm 2^\circ$.

Detection of cations/anions : A few beads of the modified resin were placed on a white spot plate. One drop of metal ion solution was then added and mixed thoroughly. The change in the colour of the beads was observed. To compare the sensitivity of the reaction, the test was also performed in the solution phase. For the detection of anions, 1–2 drops of anion solution were added to the resin bead followed by a drop of either 0.1M NaOH or 0.1M HCl to provide the alkaline or acidic medium and mixed thoroughly.

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